

Information and Quantum Free Particle Wavefunction

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In statistical mechanics it seems one has additive quantities (e.g. $e = .5m v^2$) which when placed in the power of say e to form a probability lead to product forms which are identical as long as $e_i + e_j = E$. Similar ideas occur in other statistical systems such as quantum mechanics. For example, if one decomposes a potential $V(x)$ as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and uses $\exp(ip_1x)$ as a free particle wavefunction, then for a given p one has many product scenarios $\exp(ikx)\exp(i(p-k)x)$ which yield the same result. We argue that such scenarios are a sign of equilibrium.

In this note, we consider the classical action $\int L dt$ for a free particle as information, form $\exp(i \text{Action})$ and argue that instead of using a product of probabilities as in the above examples, one may use different (p,x) and (E,t) pairs to obtain the same probability $\exp(i \text{Action})$. We argue that these have the same information i.e there is statistical equilibrium, but this suggests the special pairs are $(p, 1/p)$ and $(E, 1/E)$ where p and E represent free particle momentum and energy in either the nonrelativistic or relativistic case.. In other words there is a special length proportional to $1/p$ associated with p if one wishes to have $\exp(i \text{Action})$ values for different p 's have the same value i.e. represent the same information.

Thus $\exp(ipx)$ which follows from $\exp(i \text{Action})$ together with the notion of a wavelength i.e. special x length proportional to $1/p$ leads to probabilities with the same phase (or information) which are on the same footing and represent an equilibrium scenario. These may have different weights to create an overall distribution. Thus we argue that there may be a statistical way, related to information, to arrive at the idea of a wavelength.

The implications are important because a quantum particle in a bound state (for $p, -p$ adding as probabilities) leads to $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = 2 \cos(px)$ which means the particle has high probability to be at certain humps and very little probability in between i.e. there is a resolution in space. This seems to be a signature of quantum mechanics and is also found in the two slit experiment.

Information and Statistical Equilibrium

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be derived using the idea of reaction balance with a reaction probability equal to the product of the probabilities $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ where $f(e_i)$ is the probability to have a particle with energy $e_i = p_i^2/2m$. Thus for elastic scattering:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

A solution is $f(e_1) = C \exp(-e/T)$ ((2)) because one wishes the solution to drop to zero for high e_i .

$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ is a statement of energy conservation, but we argue that e_i may be viewed as information. For any two body collision, $e_i + e_j = E$ is the original energy and $e_k + e_l = E$ the final (for conservation). Thus all e_i, e_j pairs and all e_k, e_l pairs yield the same product probability in

equilibrium. The information placed as a power of e yields a probability function such that one has this loss of knowledge of the reactants and products as long as $e_i + e_j = E$ indicating a statistical equilibrium.

In previous notes, we extended these ideas to quantum situations such as $\exp(ikx)$ the wavefunction or conditional probability of a free particle. We argued that k takes on the idea of information such that $\exp(i k_i x) \exp(i k_j x) = \exp(i K x)$ for all $k_i + k_j = K$.

In this note, we try to argue that the form $\exp(ikx)$ itself may be a statistical form of $\exp(\text{Information})$. The information, we suggest, is the classical action for a free particle and different p, E free particle values are linked to different X, T values i.e. there are special length (wavelength) and time (frequency) values which yield identical values of $\exp(i \text{Action})$ for different p, E . Given that $\exp(i \text{Action})$ has the same value, we argue that one has a kind of statistical equilibrium. One may then take different weights of $\exp(i \text{action})$ with different p values.

Classical Action

The classical action $\int L dt$ is employed to derive the classical equations of motion by finding solutions which when varied $[v(x) \rightarrow v(x) + dv(x)]$ do not change the action i.e. it is a stationary value. For a free particle, we have suggested in previous notes that one may set $v = X/T$ and vary X and T independently to find that: $d\text{Action}/dx = p$ and $d\text{Action}/dt = -E$. This holds for both the nonrelativistic $L = .5mv^2$ and relativistic $L = -m_0 \text{sqrt}(1-v^2)$.

Writing $H = dL/dv - L$ for a free particle one obtains:

$$LT = -HT + p v T \quad \text{but } v = X/T \text{ and } H = E \quad \text{so Action} = LT = -Et + px \quad ((1))$$

This is the free particle action (nonrelativistic and relativistic) and is also a relativistic inner product of the two four vectors (E, p) and (t, x) .

We argue that Action is a kind of information and that if one wishes to have statistical equilibrium for different p, E pairs then one needs special x, t pairs namely:

$$x = b/p \quad \text{and } t = a/E \quad \text{where } b, a \text{ are constants. (In keeping with photons } a = \hbar) \quad ((2))$$

In other words special lengths (or wavelengths) must be associated with different p values in order to create probability values $\exp(ipx)$ which have the same value i.e. $\exp(i \text{phase})$. One may note that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability that extends from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$. At first this may seem as a statistical/math exercise, but the implications appear experimentally in terms of resolution (peaks and troughs).

Information and Resolution

We argue that peaks and troughs are a main signature of quantum mechanics. They are not only found in two slit interference patterns, but also in bound state wavefunctions (e.g. oscillator

solutions etc.). These suggest that a quantum particle has high probability to be in peak locations and very little probability to be in-between i.e. there is resolution

$\exp(ipx)$ which represents one dimensional motion (because p may be always placed along the x axis) is a two-dimensional object. Its modulus of one gives the impression of equal probability at each x point, but includes two dimensions which are dependent on the “wavelength” which implies nonlocality. We have argued above that this form $\exp(ipx)$ is due to taking the px portion of the free particle action with $v=X/T$. To create a probability, the information is placed in the exponent of e with appropriate constants. Here “ i ” is used as the constant which creates a periodic solution and the idea of resolution humps. The probabilities add in OR situations and act like Fourier components so classical values such as $KE(x)$ (kinetic energy) or $V(x)$ may be created from the probabilities i.e.

$$KE(x) = \frac{[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)]}{[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)]} \quad ((3))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may treat the classical action for a free particle with $v=X/T$ as information. One may use information in the power of e to obtain a probability in analogy with classical statistical mechanics (Maxwell-Boltzmann gas). Equilibrium seems to be characterized by a loss of knowledge linked to information. For example, for two body collisions the product probability $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ for any $e_i+e_j=E$ is the same i.e there is a loss of discernment characterizing equilibrium.

For the quantum case one also wishes to have this loss of discernment, but in a different manner. One wishes to have $\exp(-b \text{ Action})$ be the same for different p,E pairs. Here b is a constant which is taken to be i i.e. leads to an oscillating solution. This leads to special X and T values being chosen i.e. X is proportional to $1/p$ and T to $1/E$. This leads to different p,E pairs having the same $\exp(i \text{ phase})$ i.e. to a kind of statistical equilibrium. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ may be used for different momenta in a momentum distribution, but each p must be associated with a special length X namely the wavelength. This leads to a momentum dependent nonlocality. The periodicity leads to resolution i.e. the particle has high probability to be in peak areas, but little probability outside. The form $\exp(ipx)$ has a modulus of 1 suggesting equal probability at each x , but the two dimensions are both based on the wavelength which suggests that behind the scenes matters are different. The wavelength feature appears experimentally in the two slit experiment. Probabilities may add in OR situations so one may have different resolution schemes in various bound states, but we argue that the idea of equal information for different p,E free particle states (which is a statistical idea) may be behind this. This of course does not give the physical mechanism used to largely restrict the physical particle to peak regions.